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Earth Observation and Machine Learning as the key technologies to track implementation of the Green Deal: 10 main takeaways

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One of the key objectives of the largest government-run Earth Observation missions such as Copernicus Europe, Landsat and similar is to provide reference scientific information to enable monitoring of our changing environment across borders (and beyond visible light!). EO-based products are becoming crucial for spatial planning but also for the econometric assessment of the social benefits, taxation and political decisions in general. We have invited a number of keynote speakers and asked them to share their opinions on the general question “How can Earth Observation (EO) and Machine Learning technology help deliver the green (new) deal and what could potentially be a win-win-win situation?” By win-win-win here we imply: (1) environmental data users (businesses and organizations) win, (2) data producers win, and (3) society wins. Each of the talks was video recorded and is available [here](#). These are the main takeaways.

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Earth Observation technology for monitoring climate change

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physical, chemical and biological systems. Be it land, sea or air, EO is the most robust technology to monitor and assess the status of, and changes in, the natural and artificial environment. Particularly relevant has become its role in rapidly assessing situations during extreme weather events or natural disasters, precisely assessing Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, making EO pivotal in ensuring consistent, long-term environmental assessments in face of unpredictable climate change.

But this has come at a cost: massive data volumes produced by space-derived sensors and in-situ monitoring networks per day need to be converted into meaningful information to make use of it, while critical data is often heavily under-used because it requires a high level of technical expertise and computing capacity. Many entrepreneurs do not yet consider EO images and environmental information a commodity, and incorporating environmental information in economic assessment is considered largely underdeveloped. Joe Morrison: *“The satellite imagery industry still has no idea what customers actually want”*.

Wagemann et al. (2021) recognize the following five key challenges to finding, accessing and interoperating Big Earth Data: (1) limited processing capacity on the user side, (2) growing data volumes, (3) non-standardized data formats and dissemination workflows, (4) too many data portals, (5) difficult data discovery. Consequently, Wagemann et al. (2021) propose the following three strategies to deal with the problem:

1. **target cloud services at intermediate users** instead of policy- and decision-makers / avoid over-engineered systems with a high level of abstraction;
2. **increase capacity-building** to decrease the existing gap in cloud skills and uptake;
3. **provide a cloud certification mechanism** to increase overall trust in cloud-based services.

So, although now more than ever EO has caught the attention of the public interest, there are still barriers to making this technology accessible and easy to use: *why are EO*

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(floods, droughts etc.) as simple to use and as popular as Google Maps or AccuWeather?

Discussion forum on July 19th 2022 with online and in-person participants.

On July 19th 2022 [OpenGeoHub foundation](#) together with Wageningen University organized a public workshop entitled '*Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal*'. This is the first of a series of interactive meetings within the Horizon-Europe [Open-Earth-Monitor project](#) that aims at bringing together Earth Observation and Data experts from business, policy and academia with the community of practice, and connect with potential end-users of the future platforms developed by the project.

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after the project?

Example of a word cloud produced using Slido.com. Most voted elements of ensuring sustainability of Horizon Europe projects seem to be: reproducibility ([FAIR science](#)), user involvement, co-design, and a sustainable business model.

Each of the talks was video recorded and is available [here](#) alongside the main takeaways from the discussions.

To collect opinions from the audience we used Slido.com with its word clouds (see above) and voting tools.

We focus here on the following 10 main takeaways (subjectively chosen, please feel free to highlight your own takeaways!) that came out from the keynotes and that have been further discussed at the meeting.

#1 Tracking impacts of environmental investments is not trivial

For [Joanna Ruiter of the Netherlands Space Office \(NSO\)](#), one of the key problems of the projects funded by the NSO and the Dutch Government is that it is relatively easy to

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OEMC_19_July_2022_4_Joanna_Ruiter_wQ&A

Lessons Learned G4AW

- Two stage project
- Implement user-centered approach & digital inclusion using active M&E
- Bundling of services provide benefits (e.g. free advisory with buying inputs)
- Education & trust remain crucial success factor (e.g. farmers are more risk taking rather than to pay for insurance)

Stimulating smallholders' access to emerging AgTech and FinTech markets, Part 1: Users and Services, Summary Report 2021

- Weather information and forecast crucial
- Better soil data needed for good fertilizer advice
- Develop service delivery to be flexible for adaptations and scaling

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Ruiter, Joanna: Earth Observation Land Data & Services beyond 2022. Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal — Open-Earth-Monitor public workshop 2022, OpenGeoHub Foundation, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5446/58278>

Ruiter summarized the NSO's long-term strategy and recent national programmes, with special attention to Geodata For Agriculture and Water (G4AW; EO technology to support food security and climate resilience) programme, which includes 25 projects and innovations in 15 developing countries. In her presentation, Joanna emphasized a gap in accessibility to the many available technologies due to a lack of financing mechanisms, and the fact that new tools and EO information must be accompanied by financial services in order to have an impact in low- and middle-income countries. But the most important takeaway from her talk seems to be that there is a missing solution to efficiently track environmental investments and related impacts i.e. to make sure that funds are spent efficiently.

#2 Overlap in pre-processing of EO data is huge (and highly inefficient)

Patrick Griffiths of the European Space Agency in his talk "*EO Platforms and Open Science in Support of Green Deal Ambitions*" mentioned some of the key challenges of the EO field, for example, the data management burden affecting scientists, particularly in

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- Cloud based EO platforms can provide various abstraction levels that help scientist to cope and work more efficiently with the big EO data archives
- Currently, the European EO platform landscape suffers from redundancies and fragmentation:
 - Change of mind-set, away from project-centric thinking, towards interoperable building blocks, stop constantly "reinventing the wheel", rather reuse and build upon
 - Key technology elements are emerging via community adaptation (e.g. STAC, openEO API)
 - Advanced federation concepts can help consolidation towards an interoperable ecosystem
- The role of EO in support of the Green Deal ambitions can be considerable:
 - Upcoming and future observational capabilities together with SOTA analytics
 - Powered by federated platform ecosystem & open science:
 - Interdisciplinary data and advanced analytics
 - Explore "what if" scenarios and investigate trade-offs

THE EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY

Patrick, Griffiths: EO Platforms and open science in support of Green Deal ambitions. Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal — Open-Earth-Monitor public workshop 2022, OpenGeoHub Foundation, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5446/58301>

The scientific community could address this burden by the simplification and democratization of processes, more collaboration and sharing of data and technologies, and reducing fragmentation and redundancy of platforms; for instance, a few projects are opening up novel solutions: the [EuroData Cube](#), [OpenEO Platform](#) and [OpenEO API](#) (Schramm et al., 2021). But in essence, enormous budgets are still spent on overlapping data cleaning tasks and overlapping functionality, and this is obviously inefficient.

#3 European EO platforms suffer from redundancies and fragmentation

Patrick also concluded in his talk that “*European EO platforms suffer from redundancies and fragmentation*”. The European Commission, over the last decade, has invested significantly in EO and projects to channel EO technology into practice including commercial applications, but this has also resulted in high redundancies and many too small applications to survive the market needs. According to Patrick, what could be more efficient if we would “*stop reinventing the wheel*” and focus on collaboratively building blocks that can be easily combined and are de-centralized. This seems to

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Platform landscape to evolve in the near future:

Single monolithic infrastructure (e.g. similar to AWS, with entire Copernicus archives on spinning disk)

Federated ecosystem based on proven key technologies (e.g. STAC, openEO, Pangeo).

Continue towards an EO Platform "jungle" with redundancies and fragmentation.

Federated ecosystem of proven open source technology as a preferred solution for the future of EO in Europe.

#4 Achieving Land Degradation Neutrality requires data co-design at every stage in decision processes

Barron Orr, Lead Scientist at the UN Convention to Combat Desertification introduced the data and governance gaps in the context of achieving Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN), SDG target nr 15.3. 126 countries have pledged (or at least aim) at halting the rapid land degradation caused by damaging land uses, to ensure food security and healthy ecosystems.

In general, EO, geospatial data, and derived information play insightful roles in monitoring the SDGs targets, planning, tracking progress, and helping nations and stakeholders make informed decisions, plans, and ongoing adjustments that will contribute toward achieving the SDGs.

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Barron Orr: Data and governance gaps in the context of achieving Land Degradation Neutrality (SDG Target 15.3).

Orr described how data, and especially open data, is critical in achieving LDN since it broadens our understanding of the underlying land potential for any land use decision: for this reason data *“must be used at every stage in decision processes, crucially at the beginning in the design process, rather than only for monitoring projects already in progress”* concluded the UN scientist.

#5 Using EO data only for decisions is too risky: quality ground data helps improve EO and vice versa

Gert-Jan Nabuurs of Wageningen University and Research discussed the challenges and opportunities when better connecting the European Ground Based Forest Inventories with EO Data. With his 27 years of experience gathering ground-based data, Nabuurs recalls how our global data collection and sharing capabilities have come a long way since the beginning of his career (where he *‘had to call government agencies by phone and request floppy disks in the mail.’*)

The key takeaway from his talk: using EO data for decision making in forest inventories and planning is too risky! This is illustrated with the example of Ceccherini et al. (2020) where abrupt harvested areas detected in Finland and Sweden were due to changes in the Landsat missions and issues in the Global Forest Watch product. and

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Gert-Jan Nabuurs: Better connecting the European ground-based forest inventories with EO data; 27 years of experience with gathering ground-based data. Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal — Open-Earth-Monitor public workshop 2022, OpenGeoHub Foundation, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5446/58267>

In summary, EO-based monitoring projects should always be accompanied by a rigorous collection of field observations and appropriate statistical estimates as stated by Breidenbach et al., (2022) and also confirmed in Ceccherini et al., (2022).

The expansion of EO will require increased availability of reference surface data. Yet a number of barriers still prevent National Forest Inventories (NFI) data and similar from reaching the public eyes (despite being dominantly publicly funded). Nabuurs pointed to some promising new approaches, like the EFISCEN model for projecting forest resources under different scenarios, improved Landsat algorithms, and open source data policies throughout Europe, that are taking steps towards improving reliability and transparency in the sector (Nabuurs et al., 2022).

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Some points

- No map is unbiased – area estimates are derived from probability samples of reference data
- While no map is perfect, they should be a reliable indicator with known and quantified limitations, and so be able to support decision-making
- Algorithms need to suit the theme of interest
- Geographic domain experts with quantitative skills are needed to exploit improving characterization capabilities
- Globally consistent LCLU data allow for testing global algorithms and employing reference data to determine if and how algorithms should be disaggregated spatially
- Globally consistent LCLU data may be used off the shelf for area estimation
- Our effort is now 1/3 each of mapping, reference data analysis and field work
- EO systems need to become operational and retain core specifications that better facilitate for long-term monitoring and assessment

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Matthew Hanes: Global land cover and land use monitoring. Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal — Open-Earth-Monitor public workshop 2022, OpenGeoHub Foundation, 2022.

Another keynote, [Matt Hansen](#), the Co-Director at [Global Land Analysis and Discovery \(GLAD\)](#) lab, [spoke on Global Land Cover and Land Use Monitoring](#) and likewise emphasized that it is the primary concern for global mapping projects to have high-quality ground data to ensure unbiased estimators. No map is unbiased and no map is perfect: known and quantified limitations should be published together with the produced map.

#6 FAIR-TRUST-CARE data principles can help bridge the digital divide

[Yana Gevorgyan](#), Secretariat Director, introduced the [Group on Earth Observations \(GEO\)](#), the global network connecting government institutions, academic and research institutions, data providers, businesses, engineers, scientists and experts to create innovative solutions to global challenges based on open EO.

On top of GEO's agenda are the actions aiming at lowering the barriers for people and groups to access authoritative information, especially from countries with less access to EO data, by promoting and implementing **FAIR-TRUST-CARE** data principles:

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computers. Once the user finds the required data, it is necessary to know how it can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation. The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

- **T.R.U.S.T.:** Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology; the TRUST Principles provide a common framework to facilitate discussion and implementation of best practices in digital preservation by all stakeholders.
- The '**CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance**': Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics; the CARE principles are people and purpose-oriented, reflecting the crucial role of data in advancing Indigenous innovation and self-determination. These principles complement the existing FAIR principles encouraging open and other data movements to consider both people and purpose in their advocacy and pursuits.

These general principles have an important role to play in helping bridge the digital divide between the most developed and developing nations. Gevorgyan further discussed some of the actions GEO is taking to put these principles into action, such as working with the [Open Earth Alliance](#), to support global sustainability (and understanding) through the use of open technology solutions, and supporting agencies that offer credits for cloud technologies to low and middle-income countries.

#7 Global and local EO products nominally offering the same, can be significantly different

[Gilberto Câmara](#), former director of National Institute of Space Research in Brazil and former director of the GEO Secretariat, explored the challenges of mapping Land Use and Land Cover, highlighting the necessity of having self-consistent maps and consistent definitions of terms, like deforestation, in order to create products that are both globally trustworthy and locally relevant. Just think of the subtle visual difference between a natural and an artificial landscape, like a savanna and a cattle pasture.

Mixing or missing out on such classes in the EO product can totally change its usability

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Câmara, Gilberto: Mapping Land Use and Land Cover: The Challenges of Going Glocal. Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal — Open-Earth-Monitor public workshop 2022, OpenGeoHub Foundation, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5446/58268>

Gilberto illustrated how EO tools can fall short of being useful to policymakers at the local level when various end-users are not empowered in the development process through what he referred to as “*bottom-up map production*”. Mr Câmara pointed to the [R-based sits library](#) as an example of a commercially ready cloud services tool created with accessibility for end-users at its heart.

#8 Mapping land cover and similar general classes will stay important even though we can today also map detailed continuous variables

During the discussion session, Patrick Griffiths and Tom Hengl asked Gilberto if there is still a need for land cover maps and similar general EO products when we can now also map various continuous variables e.g. NDVI, FPAR, tree species percentage, crop types, canopy height, etc which basically represent land cover but at quantitative scales and in multivariate space, thus in much higher detail. Gilberto believes that land cover maps will remain in use because we need simple explanations of common features that people can interpret and relate to quickly: “*especially the policymakers — they need something that they can relate with*”.

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a vibrant field of research.

#9 There is always a creative way to ensure access to basic environmental ground-truth data that can then help extend research

In the [talk by Gert-Jan Nabuurs](#) we looked specifically at problems of accessing the (at least for data mining purposes) e.g. NFI Forest inventory data, which is currently kept private by national organizations and hence is not available to the majority of the research community. But there are many creative ways to access this data. Participants have mentioned strategies such as building trust — signing collaboration agreements or offering joint products that benefit both sides. The alternative is to put pressure on the governments to require that all publicly funded data is eventually released and that providing FAIR datasets should be a requirement for publication or even promotion at work.

In the recent paper by [Sabatini et al., \(2022\)](#), for example, authors have produced maps of vascular plant alpha diversity using the [sPlot database](#). These data are only available upon request by submitting a project proposal to sPlot's Steering Committee, hence the results, in principle, can neither be reproduced nor extended. Without going into reasons why this data is not available publicly (and which is often not to authors to decide), this is just one of many examples of highest quality environmental data being under embargo and research results not being FAIR.

#10 EO industry needs applications that their customers use to take action and solve problems... on a daily basis

Going back to the topic from the start of this article, in one of his (now famous) blogs, [Jim Morrison](#) (“the Controversial industry figure”) questions the sustainability of many modern EO businesses: *“lots of new analytics startups are pursuing the dangerously seductive strategy of building a new type of dataset and then closing their eyes and hoping customers will magically show up to start buying it”*. Successful businesses should instead *“build applications that their customers use to take actions and solve problems. If you use an application every day, you don't mind paying a subscription for it”*. Likewise, we also

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List terms and tests that help prove that we are dealing with Decision-Ready-Information

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Word cloud of terms most associated with Decision-Ready-Information.

Open-Earth-Monitor project

To support democratic and efficient implementation of the European Green deal (and avoid profound geopolitical turbulence's and the uncertainties brought by climate change), OpenGeoHub, together with 21 partners has launched an ambitious new European Commission-funded Horizon Europe project called “Open-Earth-Monitor” and which aims at tackling the bottlenecks in the uptake and effective usage of environmental data, both ground-observations and measurements and EO data.

The project’s main aim is to directly support European and Global sustainability frameworks, such as the ambitious European Green Deal, the European Digital

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European and global natural resources in support of decision-making and actions on the ground.

In a nutshell, over the next 4 years, the consortium will be: (1) building a cloud-based, open-source EO computing engine integrating Earth Observations with field data from pilot cases, (2) releasing FAIR data portals that seamlessly integrate existing and novel European data with global ones, (3) while involving end-users, decision-makers, landholders, SMEs and academia – throughout the design process of the tools and testing applications. Ultimately, the tools generated by the Open-Earth-Monitor Cyberinfrastructure project aim to contribute to real-world objectives and initiatives by generating use cases for testing.

The Open-Earth-Monitor Cyberinfrastructure project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under [grant agreement № 101059548](#).

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